

Circular Synergy between Biomass and Petroleum Industry in Process and Supply Chains Integration

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Abstract

The desire to decarbonize modern energy is challenged by the indispensable use of fossil fuels. Circular economy (CE) represents a promising shift of modern industry from linear towards a self-staining circular system where the synergy among various industries formulates a closed loop. Addressing the end-of-life waste hierarchy, this work evaluates the integration of biomass conversion technology as a potential strategy to empower circularity in the oil and gas (O&G) industry. Decision problems associated with technology selection and facility location are resolved using a systematic analytical approach (e.g., principal component analysis, multi-objective decision-making, mixed-integer linear programming, geospatial information, etc.) which are modelled into two parts: (i) optimal biomass conversion pathway synthesis; (ii) optimal supply chain synthesis. The performances of the determined optimal solutions in terms of the economic and environmental aspects are evaluated in the model which is then benchmarked with that of the conventional O&G design. A case study in Malaysia is adopted to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed model in determining the optimal technology pathway and supply chain. The model favors hydrogen production through gasification with promising environmental (1.32 kg CO₂/kg H₂) and economic performance (\$1.09 /kg H₂).

43 Ultimately, the proposed strategy represents a preliminary stage design which serves as a
44 direction for policymakers, investors, and researchers to strive toward CE goals.

45 **Keywords**

46 Biomass retrofitting; circular economy; sustainable supply chain management; principal
47 component analysis; multi-objective optimization; technology selection

48 **1 Introduction**

49 Non-sustainable resources play an important role in modern day energy consumption and face
50 eventual depletion through the development of civilization. Regardless of the adverse
51 environmental impact, fossil sources remain undisputed for its economic gains as compared to
52 other emerging renewable sources (solar, wind, hydro, etc.). For that reason, coal, oil and gas
53 remain indispensable and highly dependent in the modern energy mix (81.72 % in USA, 70.08 %
54 in Europe, and 87.15 % in China).¹ The shift from fossil energy is desirable but, it is illogical
55 to expect an overnight transition can be done without any negative impacts on energy security
56 and social-economic welfare.² The oil and gas (O&G) industry follows the conventional linear
57 economy of the consume-produce-dispose cycle resulting in the apparent negativity of waste
58 generation. The emerging popularity of circular economy (CE) is perceived as a promising
59 pathway towards a gradual shift towards renewables.³

60 The concept of CE depicts a regenerative system in which economic growth is differentiated
61 from environmental repercussion and retain a social benefit.⁴ Sustainable development through
62 CE reflects an effective utilization of resources to minimize waste generation, retain product
63 values, and deter from primary resources with a closed-looped resource. The potential
64 implementation of CE in the O&G industry is the integration of waste resources (e.g., biomass)
65 in the production-consumer cycle.⁵ **Figure 1** illustrates the integration of biorefinery into
66 existing O&G industries establishes circular interaction with agriculture the industry that
67 formulates a closed-looped resource. The integration of biorefinery offers effective waste
68 utilization to produce multifaceted products (e.g., bio-diesel, hydrogen, bio-ethanol, etc.)
69 which prolong resource values within the production consumer cycle.⁶ This facilitate the
70 balanced between resource natural recovery and consumption crucial in establishing CE.⁷ The
71 direct transition away from the heavily dependent fossil-based resources is challenging for the
72 socioeconomic welfare. As such, retrofitting existing infrastructures (e.g., storage, hydrotreater,
73 distillation, etc.) could pave the way towards a circular economy, representing an intermediate
74 transition that minimizes the financial and social burden.⁸

75

76 **Figure 1:** Integrated biorefinery in the O&G industry towards CE

77 The conceptualization of CE over various fields of research is different and the snowballing
 78 effect may deter from the original intended meaning.⁹ Without unanimous acceptance of CE
 79 principle in various fields, the concept implementation will be challenging with inconsistent
 80 interpretation and circular development goals. The concern over the lack of a consentaneous
 81 definition of CE induced several enthusiasts to debate the proper definition and principal of
 82 distinguishing circular from linear industry.^{10,11} This is especially critical in policy
 83 development to ensure CE goals and key performance indicators are clearly translated into
 84 business operation models. The strategic deployment of CE legislation is essential to steer key
 85 industrial players to achieve CE goals and is not driven solely by economic greed.¹² While
 86 research on CE is growing, the deployment of CE principles into national governing policies
 87 remains in its infancy stage. Existing adaptation of CE policies in several countries (e.g., UK,
 88 Finland, Singapore, Philippines, Malaysia, etc.) is unable to initiate radical transformation from
 89 linear towards circular economy but, rather, a gradual transition addressing waste management
 90 in industrial operation.¹³

91 With substantial CE research tackling policy development¹⁴ and addressing existing CE policy
 92 impact¹⁵, current literature on addressing the transition of the O&G industry towards CE is
 93 lacking. Few had attempted to associate waste utilization in various stages of O&G operations
 94 to satisfy the CE principal; such as refinery wastewater treatment utilizing industrial waste¹⁶,
 95 and drill cutting waste in cement production.¹⁷ However, these studies do not provide a
 96 strategic methodology or action plan to promote the industry's symbiosis to attain CE goals.
 97 The interaction at various levels of O&G operations (exploration mining, transportation,
 98 refining, etc.) with external industries (e.g., agriculture, petrochemical, automotive, etc.) is
 99 crucial in formulating the synergy of establishing a truly closed-looped CE.¹⁸ A recent study
 100 on closed-looped supply-chain optimization shows promising development of strategic CE
 101 implementation in the crude-derived lubricant industry.¹⁹ Alternative to the waste lubricant oil

102 refining pathway, O&G synergy with biorefineries offers promising potential for enhancing
103 network circularity.⁶

104 The integration of biorefinery technologies (including both thermochemical and biochemical
105 processes) into the O&G industry can produce useful value-added products which can be used
106 as an alternative feedstock in the existing O&G refineries. For instance, the potential of co-
107 processing biomass-derived oil (bio-oil from pyrolysis²⁰ or hydrothermal liquefaction²¹) and
108 petroleum heavy vacuum gas oil (VGO) in existing refinery configuration (e.g., catalytic
109 hydrotreatment, fluid catalytic cracking) is gaining attraction as a promising replacement for
110 fossil-based fuels.²²

111 The potential co-processing of bio-oil in existing refineries has been studied with various
112 refinery streams (e.g., cycle oil, vacuum gas oil, and atmospheric gas oil) suggesting the
113 properties of bio-oil resemble those of VGO and are therefore suitable to be blended for
114 cracking process.²³ The blending ratio of bio-oil to VGO is constrained (<10 wt.%) by the
115 technical difficulties in continuous co-production due to the poorer thermal stability of bio-oil
116 contributing to the coke formation tendency in the equipment.²⁴ Therefore, various bio-oil
117 upgrading processes (e.g., emulsification²⁵, esterification²⁶, solvent addition²⁷, and catalytic
118 hydrotreatment²⁸) are conducted prior to co-production to improve its stability by reducing the
119 oxygenated compounds in the bio-oil. Among all upgrading approaches, catalytic
120 hydrotreatment is often favored given its well-proven applicability and practicability in the oil
121 industry.²⁹ Alternatively, catalytic processes (e.g., catalytic pyrolysis, catalytic hydrothermal
122 liquefaction) can achieve better bio-oil stability which is suitable for direct co-processing with
123 VGO.³⁰ The presence of certain catalysts (usually Ni, Co, or Zeolite based) may lead to quality
124 enhancement (calorific value increased from 26.84 to 31.18 MJ/kg) but with a trade-off in
125 product yield (reduced from 44 to 36 wt.%).³¹ Nevertheless, co-processing of crude bio-oil
126 with VGO can still be effectively provided the equipment is specifically modified. For example,
127 the fluid catalytic cracking (FCC) unit can be modified in such a way that the bio-oil is fed
128 separately at a lower or stabilized temperature rather than blending it directly with existing feed
129 streams. This avoids thermal degradation of bio-oil prior to the reaction in the reactor while at
130 the same time, keeping the concentration low (<10 wt.%) to avoid coke formation.³²

131 Alternative to bio-oil integration potential, the blending of bio-ethanol (derived from biomass
132 fermentation) with petroleum fuel (e.g., gasoline, diesel, jet fuel) is another promising
133 integration pathway to establishing CE relation between agriculture and petroleum industry.³³
134 Prior to the fermentation process, pre-treatment processes (e.g., acid treatment³⁴, alkali
135 treatment³⁵, sequential acid and alkali treatment³⁶, steam and CO₂ explosion treatment³⁷) are
136 essentially needed to increase the cellulose concentration in the substrate from the breakdown
137 of complex hemicellulose and lignin structures. It is followed by enzymatic hydrolysis or
138 saccharification to cleave the large cellulose molecules into monosaccharide sugar to promote
139 ethanol production during fermentation.³⁸ Separated hydrolysis and fermentation (SHF) system
140 offers a convenient setup where, the sugary substrate is prepared through hydrolysis prior to
141 fermentation.³⁹ The production of specific inhibitors (furans and phenols) during the hydrolysis
142 stage limits the yeast activities during fermentation which resulted in lower bio-ethanol yield.⁴⁰
143 To overcome such fermentation difficulty, saccharification and fermentation (SSF) system is
144 introduced with both hydrolysis and fermentation operating simultaneously within a single
145 reactor. This offers a superior performance producing a higher ethanol concentration yield
146 (6.05 % in 24 hours) relative to SHF (4.74 % in 72 hours).⁴¹ Furthermore, the effluent produced

147 after bio-ethanol extraction can serve as feedstock for the anaerobic digestion (AD) which
148 enables the co-production of bio-ethanol and methane.⁴²

149 AD utilizes microbial activities to digest any organic matter in the absence of oxygen to
150 produce methane-rich gas (biogas).⁴³ Biogas composes mostly of methane (53-70 vol%) and
151 carbon dioxide (30-70 vol%) with a small trace of oxygen (0-5 vol%) and nitrogen (2-6
152 vol%).⁴⁴ Further purification of biogas is required to enhance the purity of methane (bio-
153 methane) through the removal of impurities such as carbon dioxide and nitrogen (e.g.,
154 membrane separation⁴⁵, pressure swing absorption (PSA)⁴⁶). Bio-methane (55.5 MJ/kg) has a
155 potential replacement for natural gas (52.2 MJ/kg) as fuel, and also can be further reformed
156 into hydrogen through steam reforming technique (e.g., sorption enhance steam reforming⁴⁷,
157 catalytic steam reforming⁴⁸, membrane steam reforming⁴⁹). As an alternative to biogas
158 production through a biochemical process, synthetic gas (syngas) is obtained from
159 thermochemical approaches, primarily through gasification. In contrast to bio-gas, syngas is
160 rich in hydrogen (35 vol%) and some amount of methane (13 vol%) which can undergo
161 purification to obtain purer hydrogen.⁵⁰ Various syngas upgrading techniques include
162 membrane separation⁵¹ and pressure swing adsorption⁵² to purify the gas of impurities to obtain
163 pure hydrogen. Furthermore, the addition of catalytic (Ni, Co, or Zeolite based) in the
164 gasification process enhances the concentration of hydrogen in syngas with the sacrificial
165 product yield.⁵³ Gaseous products derived from biomass offer a potential sustainable fuel and
166 hydrogen source which is a cornerstone resource in refining processes (e.g., hydrotreatment,
167 hydrocracking, etc.).

168 Despite the substantial potential benefit of intensifying O&G processes as a driver towards CE
169 goals, commercial implementation remains challenging due to a lack of comprehensive
170 methodology and guidelines to persuade decision-makers.⁵⁴ Existing literature on CE
171 implementation in the O&G industry is still in its early stages (e.g., development of circular
172 framework business model, discussing key principles, and acceptable definition) and lacks
173 contribution to evaluating the CE transition of O&G industry influences in terms of economic
174 and sustainability. Synthesis of the biomass supply chain⁵⁵ and technology selection⁵⁶ have
175 been addressed in existing literature, but these works did not contribute to assessing the
176 sustainability of integrating biorefinery in the O&G industry as drivers towards CE vision.
177 With that, this works attempts to close the aforementioned gap by developing a novel optimization
178 framework to formulate and evaluate the integration of biorefinery in the O&G industry
179 towards CE

180 **2 Problem Statement**

181 This work extends the formulated supply-chain problems from prior work on waste oil re-
182 refinery⁵⁷ to consider the coast-to-coast interaction, which reflects the realistic scenario of
183 domestic sea transport. The proposed problem comprises two separated regions denoted as East
184 (e) and West (w) which, are interactable only by sea transport. **Figure 2** illustrates the generic
185 superstructure representing the stated problem, which modelled the biomass strategy
186 addressing both the technology selection and facility location problem. The superstructure is
187 formulated starting with the biomass supplies ($s_e \in S_e$ and $s_w \in S_w$) that are delivered to
188 potential production facilities ($f_e \in F_e$ and $f_w \in F_w$) and/or shipped to port ($p_e \in P_e$ and $p_w \in$
189 P_w) as raw feedstock ($a \in A$). The feedstock (a) is processed into intermediates ($b \in B$)
190 followed by the final products ($c \in C$) *via* various technological pathways ($g \in G$ for biomass
191 conversion, and $h \in H$ for product upgrading). Furthermore, the raw feedstock (a) and the
192 produced products (c) can be delivered to both East and West Malaysia production facilities
193 (f_e and f_w) and/or crude oil refineries ($r_e \in R_e$ and $r_w \in R_w$) *via* sea transportation (p). In
194 addition, surplus products (c) can be transferred to oil terminals ($t_e \in T_e$ and $t_w \in T_w$) for
195 potential exportation. Similar to the prior work, the proposed model to retrofit existing crude
196 oil refineries with biomass technology aims to devise strategies for circularity concerning a
197 balanced economic and environmental trade-off. Hence, this paper proposes the integration of
198 biomass sources in the existing O&G industry supply chain to achieve a sustainable industry
199 with a circular flow of resources.

200

201 **Figure 2:** Generic superstructure modelled in the biomass supply chain.

202 **3 Methodology**

203 **Figure 3** illustrates the research flowchart to formulate an optimized biomass retrofitting
204 strategy addressing both the technology pathway and facility location problems. Prior to the
205 model development, essential information (e.g., biomass retrofitting pathways, geographical
206 information, transportation, etc.) is collected through literature (e.g., Springer, Elsevier, Wiley,
207 etc.) and geographical information system (GIS) database services (Google Map, Malaysia
208 Palm Oil Board, Open Street Map, Open Route Service). This work addresses the problems on
209 two scales which are subsequently modelled as: Model I (PCA-aided decision-making analysis
210 on biomass integration pathways); and Model II (integrated biorefinery facilities location in
211 supply chain network) to reduce the problem complexity and required computational time and
212 effort. In Model I, various biomass integration pathways are explored and considered to
213 determine and evaluate for the optimal technology pathway utilizing the novel PCA-aided
214 MODM optimization approach.⁵⁸ The model considers various decision criteria (e.g., revenue,
215 operating (OPEX), capital expenditure (CAPEX), carbon emissions, and energy consumption),
216 which are essential for decision-makers in achieving the desired economic and environmental
217 goals. A greater number of criteria will translate to greater complexity in the decision-making,
218 dimension reduction is performed by evaluating fewer variables (in the form of Principal
219 Components, PCs) while ensuring information loss is minimal yet sufficient to describe the
220 problem.⁵⁹ The dimensionally reduced PCs (featured PCs) are evaluated to synthesize the
221 optimal biomass integration pathways which provide insights into plant-level design. Moving
222 on to Model II, the facility location problem is addressed with geospatial information relative
223 to the case study to represent a realistic supply-chain system. The model takes on the Mixed-
224 Integer Linear Programming (MILP) approach with the primary aim of minimizing cost
225 relative to transportation and new capital activities. The optimal number of facilities is justified
226 with the optimal tradeoff between both objectives' performance. Lastly, the performances of
227 the proposed circular biomass retrofitting strategy are evaluated and benchmarked with the
228 conventional linear industry. Further details of the model development are discussed in the
229 following subsections.

230

231 **Figure 3:** Research flowchart for determining optimal technology and supply chain design for
 232 biorefinery integration in O&G industry towards CE

233

234 **3.1 Model I: PCA-aided decision-making analysis on biomass integration** 235 **pathways**

236 This model evaluates various biomass retrofitting pathways for O&G industry using the novel
 237 PCA-aided MODM approach.⁶⁰ **Figure 4** illustrates the PCA-aided MODM approach to
 238 determine the optimal biomass retrofitting pathway: (1) Data collection and processing; (2)
 239 Dimension reduction; (3) PCs optimize direction (maximize or minimize); (4) Compute
 240 weighted sum approach. In general, the method started with data processing (standardization)
 241 which is a prerequisite for the elimination of the scale differences between variables. The
 242 following steps identify the correlation between the respective decision criteria. Based on the
 243 correlation, the eigenvalue (magnitude) and eigenvector (direction) are utilized in the
 244 dimension reduction and identifying the corresponding PC optimization direction (either
 245 maximize or minimize). Lastly, the respective PCs scores are calculated and synthesized for
 246 the corresponding pathways' performance, which is ranked to identify the optimal biomass

247 technology selection. Further details of the PCA method are discussed in the following
 248 subsections.

249

250 **Figure 4:** Model I flowchart for PCA-aided MODM approach

251 **3.1.1 Balanced material conversion**

252 This section presents the material balance equations that reflect the conversion of raw feedstock
 253 (a) into final products (c). Equations (1) to (4) indicate the input material flow (feedstock
 254 ($F_{f_e,g,a}, F_{f_w,g,a}$) [t/year] and intermediate ($F_{f_e,h,b}, F_{f_w,h,b}$) [t/year] to the respective biomass
 255 conversion technologies (h, g) assumed constant without loss of material between feed transfer.

256
$$F_{f_e,a} = \sum_g F_{f_e,g,a} \quad \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall a \in A \quad (1)$$

257
$$F_{f_e,b} = \sum_h F_{f_e,h,b} \quad \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall b \in B \quad (2)$$

258
$$F_{f_w,a} = \sum_g F_{f_w,g,a} \quad \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall a \in A \quad (3)$$

259
$$F_{f_w,b} = \sum_h F_{f_w,h,b} \quad \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall b \in B \quad (4)$$

260 Furthermore, the mass balance equations across each process (g and h) are mathematically
 261 expressed in Equations (5) to (8), where the corresponding conversion ratios in process g

262 (convert a into b) and h (convert b into p) are denoted as $X_{g,a \rightarrow b}$ and $X_{h,b \rightarrow c}$ from raw biomass
 263 waste (a) to intermediate (b) the final products (c) are mathematically expressed. The
 264 feed/product amount in each stage of the process is expressed as $F_{f_e,g,a}$, $F_{f_w,g,a}$ and $F_{f_e,h,b}$,
 265 $F_{f_w,h,b}$. These equations ensure no products/mass is lost in between the respective blocks except
 266 during the product conversion.

$$267 \quad F_{f_e,b} = \sum_g \sum_a (F_{f_e,g,a} \times X_{g,a \rightarrow b}) \quad \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall b \in B \quad (5)$$

$$268 \quad F_{f_e,c} = \sum_h \sum_b (F_{f_e,h,b} \times X_{h,b \rightarrow c}) \quad \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall c \in C \quad (6)$$

$$269 \quad F_{f_w,b} = \sum_g \sum_a (F_{f_w,g,a} \times X_{g,a \rightarrow b}) \quad \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall b \in B \quad (7)$$

$$270 \quad F_{f_w,c} = \sum_h \sum_b (F_{f_w,h,b} \times X_{h,b \rightarrow c}) \quad \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall c \in C \quad (8)$$

271 3.1.2 PCA-aided MODM approach for technology selection

272 The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is introduced as a multivariate statistical method
 273 that compresses information with large series of correlated variables into smaller sets of
 274 uncorrelated variables, which are denoted as principal components (PCs).⁶¹ The key advantage
 275 of PCA is the size reduction of information which resulted in a tradeoff of losing some
 276 information for a significant reduction in data size, thus reducing the variable redundancy of a
 277 given set of information. Furthermore, this work follows the extension of a novel PCA
 278 application as multi-objective decision-making (MODM) analysis to evaluate various solutions
 279 for the n-number of optimal solutions based on the performance score.^{58,60} To compute the
 280 method, a decision matrix (Z) is established with the combined parameters (y_{ij}) representing
 281 the technology combination (i) and the respective criteria (j), where I and J refer to the total
 282 number of technology and criteria involved in the study (see Equation (9)).

$$283 \quad Z = \begin{bmatrix} y_{0,0} & y_{0,1} & \cdots & y_{0,j} \\ y_{1,0} & y_{1,1} & \cdots & y_{1,j} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ y_{i,0} & y_{i,1} & \cdots & y_{i,j} \end{bmatrix}_{I \times J} \quad (9)$$

284 The technology criteria (j) is expressed in various units in which standardization (centered and
 285 scaled) of Z matrix is needed to achieve a unitless comparison (see Equation (10)). Where, μ_j
 286 denotes the mean and σ_j denotes the standard deviation of respective criteria (j). This ensures
 287 the measurement for the relation between each criterion is relative to the same origin and scaled
 288 to eliminate the dominance of criteria due to scales of unit (e.g., kg, \$, kWh, etc.).

$$289 \quad Z_{std} = \frac{y_{ij} - \mu_j}{\sigma_j} \quad (10)$$

290 The relative relationship of each criterion to one another can be evaluated as the correlation
 291 matrix (R) in Equation (11), where Z_{std}^T denotes the transposed standardized matrix Z_{std} . This
 292 encapsulates the criterion into PCs which enables the assessment of non-correlated PCs as

293 objectives suitable for dimension reduction. Note, the correlation matrix R is mean centered
 294 before decomposition.⁶²

$$295 \quad R = Z_{std}^T \cdot Z_{std} \quad (11)$$

296 This is followed by the decomposition of the correlation matrix (R) using singular value
 297 decomposition (SVD) into U (left singular matrix), V (right singular matrix), and Σ (diagonal
 298 matrix) (see Equation (12)).

$$299 \quad R = U\Sigma V^T \quad (12)$$

300 Considering the eigenvector-eigenvalue decomposition of the correlation matrix (R) (see
 301 Equation (13)), the standardized data is decomposed *via* SVD into its directional and magnitude
 302 using Equation (14) (substitute Equation (12) into Equation (13)), where V is interpreted as the
 303 eigenvectors and, λ is denoted as the eigenvalues ($\lambda = \Sigma^2$).⁶³ The sign ambiguity of SVD
 304 is addressed following the demonstration conducted by Bro *et al.*⁶⁴ to ensure the resulting
 305 loading sign of the eigenvectors V is stable.

$$306 \quad R^T \cdot R = V\lambda V^T \quad (13)$$

$$307 \quad U\Sigma V^T U^T \Sigma V = V\Sigma^2 V^T = V\lambda V^T \quad (14)$$

308 The eigenvector V represents the loadings of the scaled data (Z_{std}) projected onto a new
 309 Euclidean space (PCs) which re-evaluates the projection vector based on the preferential
 310 optimize direction (positive or negative) of each criterion (see Equation (15) to (20)). The
 311 eigenvalues (λ) measure the variance of respective criterion contribution to the PCs and
 312 dimension reduction is performed to identify the featured PCs (see Equations (21) to (23)). To
 313 retain the preferential direction of the original variables (maximize or minimize), the PCs
 314 projections are re-evaluated based on each criterion contribution weights to the respective PCs
 315 (see Equation (15)), where $v_{j,k}$ denotes the eigenvector (V) with the corresponding j criteria
 316 and the k th PCs (see Equation (16)).

$$317 \quad Contribution_{j,k} = \frac{(v_{j,k})^2}{\sum_j (v_{j,k})^2} \times 100 \quad \forall j \in J, \forall k \in K \quad (15)$$

$$318 \quad V = \begin{bmatrix} v_{0,0} & v_{0,1} & \cdots & v_{0,k} \\ v_{1,0} & v_{1,1} & \cdots & v_{1,k} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ v_{j,0} & v_{j,1} & \cdots & v_{j,k} \end{bmatrix}_{J \times K} \quad (16)$$

319 The projected PCs direction (positive or negative) is identified indicating the directly (+) or
 320 inversely proportional (-) relationship of each criterion in the respective PCs axes (see
 321 Equation (17) as an example).

$$322 \quad V = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ -3 & 4 & -1 \\ 4 & -2 & -4 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow Sign(V) = \begin{bmatrix} + & + & + \\ - & + & - \\ + & - & - \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

323 The determination of a PCs optimization direction is demonstrated in **Table 1**. Given three
 324 variables, the projection sign indicates each criterion directly (+) or inversely (–)related to
 325 the respective PCs. Next, the sign multiplication between the correlation and preference (either
 326 maximize (+) or minimize (–) variable) follows the sign rules where an identical sign will
 327 result in a positive score outcome (e.g., (–) × (–) = (+)), or otherwise, a negative outcome
 328 will be obtained. Hence, the net score is calculated as the sum total of all the variables with the
 329 corresponding contribution from Equation (15). The net weight is then used as an indicator to
 330 decide whether the respective PCs should be maximized or minimized. If it is greater than zero
 331 (> 0), the PC should be maximized (+); while if otherwise, it should be minimized (–).

332 **Table 1:** PCs Optimization Direction Demonstration⁵⁸

Variables	Sign of Loading, V	Preference	Contribution [%]	Weights
V_1	+	+	10	+ 10
V_2	-	-	50	+ 50
V_3	+	-	40	- 40
Net Weight =				+ 20 (> 0)
PCs Optimization Direction =				Maximize

333 The PCs score (S) is calculated as the dot product between the scaled data (Z_{std}) and the PCs
 334 loadings (V) as shown in Equation (18).

$$335 \quad S = Z_{std} \cdot V \quad (18)$$

336 Depending on the PCs optimization direction (either to be maximized or minimized), the
 337 degree of satisfaction ($\mu_{i,k}$) of the respective technology pathway (i) and the corresponding
 338 PCs (k) is calculated using Equation (19) where, $x_{k_{min}}$ and $x_{k_{max}}$ denotes the minimal and
 339 maximal k th PCs score (S) (see Equation (20)).

$$340 \quad \mu_{i,k} = \begin{cases} \frac{x_{i,k} - x_{k_{min}}}{x_{k_{max}} - x_{k_{min}}} \Big|_{maximize} & \forall i \in I, \forall k \in K \\ \frac{x_{k_{max}} - x_{i,k}}{x_{k_{max}} - x_{k_{min}}} \Big|_{minimize} & \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

$$341 \quad S = \begin{bmatrix} x_{0,0} & x_{0,1} & \cdots & x_{0,k} \\ x_{1,0} & x_{1,1} & \cdots & x_{1,k} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{i,0} & x_{i,1} & \cdots & x_{i,k} \end{bmatrix}_{I \times K} \quad (20)$$

342 Furthermore, the dimension reduction is performed using the eigenvector to identify the
 343 optimal number of PCs to retain. To achieve this, the explained variance (VAR_k) for the k
 344 number of PCs are calculated by the eigenvalues (λ_k) of respective PCs divided by the sum of
 345 all eigenvalues ($\sum_k \lambda_k$) (see Equation (21)).

346
$$VAR_k = \frac{\lambda_k}{\sum_k \lambda_k} \quad \forall k \in K \quad (21)$$

347 A threshold of 90%⁵⁸ of total cumulative variance (*CVAR*) is set to ensure the selected *k'*th
 348 number of PCs (featured PCs) preserving most of the information to describe the problem (see
 349 Equation (22)).

350
$$CVAR = \sum_{k'} VAR_{k'} \geq 90\% \quad (22)$$

351 The *k'* number of featured PCs, the corresponding PCs priority ($P_{k'}$) is calculated using
 352 Equation (23) with the respective explained variance ($VAR_{k'}$) divided by the cumulative
 353 variance of the *k'* number of featured PCs.

354
$$P_{k'} = \frac{VAR_{k'}}{CVAR} \quad \forall k' \in K' \quad (23)$$

355 The objective function (*Objective*) represents the maximization of the weighted sum
 356 approach as shown in Equation (24) where, the featured PCs degree of satisfaction ($\mu_{k'}$)
 357 are scaled based on the corresponding featured PCs priority ($P_{k'}$).

358
$$Objective = max \sum_{k'} (\mu_{k'} \times P_{k'}), \quad (24)$$

359 **3.2 Model II: Integrated biorefinery facilities location in supply chain** 360 **network**

361 This model aims to propose the optimal design of the biomass supply chain addressing the
 362 facility location problem. **Figure 5** presents the flowchart to integrate biorefinery facilities'
 363 location in supply chain networks. Prior to the model formulation, open-sourced geospatial
 364 information system (GIS) services (Google Map, OpenStreetMap, Malaysia Palm Oil Board,
 365 OpenRouteService) are utilized in acquiring accurate geographical data which enables the
 366 modelled problem to reflect closely to the actual scenario.^{65,66} The facility location problem is
 367 modelled as a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem and solved utilizing Google
 368 open-sourced optimization solver libraries called 'ortools'.⁶⁷ Furthermore, the optimal number
 369 of facilities is identified with respect to the objectives' performances and justifies the optimal
 370 solution allocated facilities and supply-chain network design.

371

372 **Figure 5:** Model II flowchart for integrated biorefinery facilities location in the supply chain
 373 network

374 3.2.1 Model constrains

375 The supplies (s_e , s_w) is modelled to be delivered to production facilities (f_e , f_w) and ports
 376 (p_e , p_w) for domestic sea transport. As such, the total delivered feed (a) amount from suppliers
 377 to facilities ($Q_{s_e, f_e, a}$) [t/year] and ports ($Q_{s_e, p_e, a}$) [t/year] is constrained to be not more than the
 378 supplier's available feed amount ($Q_{s_e, a}$, $Q_{s_w, a}$) [t/year] (see Equations (25) and (26)).

$$379 \quad \sum_{f_e} Q_{s_e, f_e, a} + \sum_{p_e} Q_{s_e, p_e, a} \leq Q_{s_e, a}, \quad \forall s_e \in S_e, \forall a \in A \quad (25)$$

$$380 \quad \sum_{f_w} Q_{s_w, f_w, a} + \sum_{p_w} Q_{s_w, p_w, a} \leq Q_{s_w, a}, \quad \forall s_w \in S_w, \forall a \in A \quad (26)$$

381 The model is given the flexibility to select which facilities (f_e , f_w) to be operational
 382 considering both distance and production capacity. As such, the 'Big M' constrain is adopted
 383 to restrict the flow of resources only to the selected facilities denoted by the binary variables
 384 (B_{f_e} , B_{f_w}). Instead of using an ambiguously large 'M' number, the total feed availability ($Q_{s_e, a}$,
 385 $Q_{s_w, a}$) [t/year] is used instead to reduce the unnecessary computational burden (see Equations
 386 (27) and (28)).

$$387 \quad Q_{s_e, f_e, a} \leq Q_{s_e, a} \times B_{f_e}, \quad \forall s_e \in S_e, \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall a \in A \quad (27)$$

$$388 \quad Q_{s_w, f_w, a} \leq Q_{s_w, a} \times B_{f_w}, \quad \forall s_w \in S_w, \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall a \in A \quad (28)$$

389 The amount of raw biomass supplied (a) to the production facilities ($Q_{f_e, a}$, $Q_{f_w, a}$) [t/year] is
 390 equal to the total amount supplied by the local suppliers ($Q_{s_e, f_e, a}$, $Q_{s_w, f_w, a}$) [t/year] and
 391 domestically shipped amount ($Q_{p_e, f_e, a}$, $Q_{p_w, f_w, a}$) [t/year] as shown in Equations (29) and (30).

$$392 \quad Q_{f_e, a} = \sum_{s_e} Q_{s_e, f_e, a} + \sum_{p_e} Q_{p_e, f_e, a}, \quad \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall a \in A \quad (29)$$

$$393 \quad Q_{f_w, a} = \sum_{s_w} Q_{s_w, f_w, a} + \sum_{p_w} Q_{p_w, f_w, a}, \quad \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall a \in A \quad (30)$$

394 The amount of products (c) produced by the facility ($Q_{f_e,c}, Q_{f_w,c}$) [t/year] is calculated using
 395 Equations (31) and (32) where, $Q_{f_e,a}$ [t/year] and $Q_{f_w,a}$ [t/year] denote the total feedstock
 396 received by the facility at the east and west region, respectively (from Equation (29) and (30))
 397 while $X_{a \rightarrow c}$ [wt.%] is the mass conversion rate from feed (a) to the final products (c)
 398 (simplified from Equations (5) to (8)).

$$399 \quad Q_{f_e,c} = \sum_a Q_{f_e,a} X_{a \rightarrow c} \quad , \quad \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall c \in C \quad (31)$$

$$400 \quad Q_{f_w,c} = \sum_a Q_{f_w,a} X_{a \rightarrow c} \quad , \quad \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall c \in C \quad (32)$$

401 Furthermore, the produced products (c) are delivered to refineries ($Q_{f_e,r_e,c}, Q_{f_w,r_w,c}$) [t/year],
 402 oil terminals ($Q_{f_e,t_e,c}, Q_{f_w,t_w,c}$) [t/year], and ports ($Q_{f_e,p_e,c}, Q_{f_w,p_w,c}$) [t/year] are constrained by
 403 the total amount of production ($Q_{f_e,c}, Q_{f_w,c}$) [t/year] (see Equations (33) and (34)).

$$404 \quad \sum_{r_e} Q_{f_e,r_e,c} + \sum_{t_e} Q_{f_e,t_e,c} + \sum_{p_e} Q_{f_e,p_e,c} = Q_{f_e,c} \quad , \quad \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall c \in C \quad (33)$$

$$405 \quad \sum_{r_w} Q_{f_w,r_w,c} + \sum_{t_w} Q_{f_w,t_w,c} + \sum_{p_w} Q_{f_w,p_w,c} = Q_{f_w,c} \quad , \quad \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall c \in C \quad (34)$$

406 To ensure the refinery demands are satisfied ($Q_{r_e,c}, Q_{r_w,c}$) [t/year], the transportation of
 407 produced ($Q_{f_e,r_e,c}, Q_{f_w,r_w,c}$) [t/year] and imported products ($Q_{f_e,p_e,c}, Q_{f_w,p_w,c}$) [t/year] are
 408 constrained with Equation (35) and (36).

$$409 \quad \sum_{f_e} Q_{f_e,r_e,c} + \sum_{p_e} Q_{p_e,r_e,c} = Q_{r_e,c} \quad , \quad \forall r_e \in R_e, \forall c \in C \quad (35)$$

$$410 \quad \sum_{f_w} Q_{f_w,r_w,c} + \sum_{p_w} Q_{p_w,r_w,c} = Q_{r_w,c} \quad , \quad \forall r_w \in R_w, \forall c \in C \quad (36)$$

411 Equations (37) to (40) constrain the flow of materials between East and West Malaysia to
 412 ensure the amount delivered is equal to the total amount received at the port for both raw
 413 feedstocks ($Q_{s_e,p_e,a}, Q_{s_w,p_w,a}$) [t/year] and processed products ($Q_{f_e,p_e,c}, Q_{f_w,p_w,c}$) [t/year]. Note
 414 that the material streams from East to West port (p_e, p_w) ($Q_{p_e,p_w,a}, Q_{p_e,p_w,c}$) [t/year] and West
 415 to East port (p_w, p_e) ($Q_{p_w,p_e,a}, Q_{p_w,p_e,c}$) [t/year] are indicated with different indexes.

$$416 \quad \sum_{p_w} Q_{p_e,p_w,a} = \sum_{s_e} Q_{s_e,p_e,a} \quad \forall p_e \in P_e, \forall a \in A \quad (37)$$

$$417 \quad \sum_{p_w} Q_{p_e,p_w,c} = \sum_{f_e} Q_{f_e,p_e,c} \quad \forall p_e \in P_e, \forall c \in C \quad (38)$$

$$418 \quad \sum_{p_e} Q_{p_w,p_e,a} = \sum_{s_w} Q_{s_w,p_w,a} \quad \forall p_w \in P_w, \forall a \in A \quad (39)$$

$$419 \quad \sum_{p_e} Q_{p_w,p_e,c} = \sum_{f_w} Q_{f_w,p_w,c} \quad \forall p_w \in P_w, \forall c \in C \quad (40)$$

420 Equations (41) and (42) ensure the total imported raw feedstocks ($Q_{p_e,p_w,a}, Q_{p_w,p_e,a}$) [t/year] is
 421 transported to the production facilities ($Q_{p_e,f_e,a}, Q_{p_w,f_w,a}$) [t/year] for processing. Similarly, the
 422 ‘Big M’ approach is utilized to ensure the imported materials are delivered only to the selected
 423 production facilities (B_{f_e}, B_{f_w}) (see Equations (43) and (44))

$$424 \quad \sum_{f_e} Q_{p_e,f_e,a} = \sum_{p_w} Q_{p_w,p_e,a} \quad \forall p_e \in P_e, \forall a \in A \quad (41)$$

425
$$\sum_{f_w} Q_{p_w, f_w, a} = \sum_{p_e} Q_{p_e, p_w, a} \quad \forall p_w \in P_w, \forall a \in A \quad (42)$$

426
$$Q_{p_e, f_e, a} \leq M \times B_{f_e} \quad \forall p_e \in P_e, \forall f_e \in F_e, \forall a \in A \quad (43)$$

427
$$Q_{p_w, f_w, a} \leq M \times B_{f_w} \quad \forall p_w \in P_w, \forall f_w \in F_w, \forall a \in A \quad (44)$$

428 Equations (45) and (46) ensure the total delivered products (c) from the port to the refineries
 429 ($Q_{p_e, r_e, c}, Q_{p_w, r_w, c}$) [t/year] and oil terminals ($Q_{p_e, t_e, c}, Q_{p_w, t_w, c}$) [t/year] is equal to the total
 430 imported amount ($Q_{p_w, p_e, c}, Q_{p_e, p_w, c}$) [t/year].

431
$$\sum_{r_e} Q_{p_e, r_e, c} + \sum_{t_e} Q_{p_e, t_e, c} = \sum_{p_w} Q_{p_w, p_e, c} \quad \forall p_e \in P_e, \forall c \in C \quad (45)$$

432
$$\sum_{r_w} Q_{p_w, r_w, c} + \sum_{t_w} Q_{p_w, t_w, c} = \sum_{p_e} Q_{p_e, p_w, c} \quad \forall p_w \in P_w, \forall c \in C \quad (46)$$

433 Lastly, the model may be given an additional constrain to restrict the total number of facilities
 434 selected ($N_{f_e + f_w}$) to enable the analysis and comparing the number of facilities to the optimal
 435 solutions (see Equation (47)).

436
$$\sum_{f_e} B_{f_e} + \sum_{f_w} B_{f_w} = N_{f_e + f_w} \quad (47)$$

437 3.2.2 Objective function

438 The objective function (F^{obj}) [\$/year] evaluates the economic performance based on the cost
 439 reduction of annualized capital investment from production facilities ($Cost^{fac}$) [\$/year] and
 440 transportation activities ($Cost^{tr}$) [\$/year] (see Equation (48)).

441
$$F^{obj} = Cost^{fac} + Cost^{tr} \quad (48)$$

442 Considering the six-tenth rule of capital estimation is unable to be modelled in the MILP model,
 443 efforts were done to linearize the capital estimation. Equation (49) shows the linearized capital
 444 cost function taking the production capacity ($Product^{fac}$) [t/year] and the facility operational
 445 variable ($Binary^{fac}$).

446
$$Cost^{fac} = LinearCAPEX(Product^{fac}, Binary^{fac}) \quad (49)$$

447 The linearized capital cost function is formulated with a simple linear function where m is the
 448 gradient, x is the production capacity, c is the intersection point, B is the binary variable
 449 indication if the production facility is operational, and the cost recovery factor (CRF) is used
 450 to annualize the capital cost (see Equation (50)).

451
$$LinearCAPEX(x, B) = (mx + cB) \times CRF \quad (50)$$

452 Equation (51) is used to calculate the CRF, where in refers to the interest rate (7%), while LS
 453 denotes the life span of the study (20 years).

454
$$CRF = \frac{in(1-in)^{LS}}{(1-in)^{LS}-1} \quad (51)$$

455 The transportation cost ($Cost^{tr}$) [\$/year] is calculated by the distance travelled for round trips
456 (Dis^{tr}) [km] multiplied by the amount transported (Amt^{tr}) [t/year] and the cost of
457 transportation fuel rate (CR^{tr}) [\$/t·km] (see Equation (52)).

$$458 \quad Cost^{tr} = Dis^{tr} \times Amt^{tr} \times CR^{tr} \quad (52)$$

459 Notably, the total carbon emissions (Emi^{total}) [kg CO₂/year] is attributed to the production
460 (Emi^{fac}) [kg CO₂/year] and transportation activities (Emi^{tr}) [kg CO₂/year] (see Equation
461 (53)). Equation (54) express the emission associated to production process which is dependent
462 on the feed amount processed (Amt^{fac}) [t/year] and the rate of emission (ER^{fac}) [kg CO₂/t].
463 Similarly, transportation contributed emission is based on the amount (Amt^{tr}) [t/year]
464 transported over a round trip distance (Dis^{tr}) [km] and the vehicle rate of emission (ER^{tr}) [kg
465 CO₂/t·km] (see Equation (55)).

$$466 \quad Emi^{total} = Emi^{fac} + Emi^{tr} \quad (53)$$

$$467 \quad Emi^{fac} = Amt^{fac} \times ER^{fac} \quad (54)$$

$$468 \quad Emi^{tr} = Dis^{tr} \times Amt^{tr} \times ER^{tr} \quad (55)$$

469 **4 Case Study Descriptions**

470 Malaysia is designated as the case study in this work to demonstrate the effectiveness of the
471 formulated model. An estimated 88,820,076 tons of fresh fruit bunch (FFB) harvested in the
472 year 2021 produces 45,466,997 tons of biomass residues.⁶⁶ Based on the harvested FFB, the
473 generated biomass is composed of oil palm frond (OPF 45.69 wt.%), mesocarp fiber (MF 15.98
474 wt.%), empty fruit bunch (EFB 15.20 wt.%), palm kernel shell (PKS 9.22 wt.%), oil palm trunk
475 (OPT 7.31 wt.%), and palm oil mill effluent (POME 6.60 wt.%).⁶⁸ The utilization of geospatial
476 data enables the accurate estimation of transport distance and reflects the real-life scenario.
477 **Figure 6** illustrates the various point of interest throughout Malaysia with 444 palm oil mills
478 (i.e., the biomass supply), 1,852 designated industrial zones (i.e., the potential locations for
479 new facilities), 11 ports (i.e., the maritime facilities), 5 crude oil refineries, and 13 oil terminals
480 (i.e., the potential product sinks) are incorporated into the model as reflected in the generic
481 superstructure from **Figure 2**. The assumptions made to the supply-chain model (e.g.,
482 linearized capital investment, operating cost, transportation, product price, etc.) are
483 documented in the Supporting Information **Table S1** to **Table S3**. Furthermore, the developed
484 model has been published and made open-sourced at Yeo *et al.*⁶⁹

485

486 **Figure 6:** Geospatial data for biomass supply-chain

487 **Figure 7** illustrates the possible biomass retrofitting pathway which constitutes the technology
 488 selection problem within the subset ($f \in F$) of the generic superstructure (see **Figure 2**).
 489 Various types of biomasses (EFB, PKS, and OPF) are fed into a set of available biomass
 490 conversion technologies, which cover both thermochemical (i.e., pyrolysis, gasification,
 491 liquefaction, hydrocracking, etc.) and biological pathways (anaerobic digestion, enzymatic
 492 hydrolysis, etc.). A set of valuable products (e.g., jet fuel⁷⁰, hydrogen⁷¹, gasoline⁷²) which can
 493 be integrated into the conventional oil and gas industry are then generated from the
 494 aforementioned technologies. For example, hydrogen derived from syngas (gasification) or
 495 biogas (anaerobic digestion) is valuable for certain crude oil processes (e.g., hydrocracking,
 496 hydrotreatment, hydro-desulphurization, etc.). On the other hand, raw bio-oil produced from
 497 pyrolysis can be further upgraded via the hydrotreating process to improve the stability of the
 498 bio-oil. It can then be fed into the downstream refinery FCC unit alongside VGO (bio-oil mix
 499 < 10 wt.%) to produce transportation fuels (gasoline, jet fuel, and diesel). Alternatively, with
 500 some modifications to the FCC unit which can avoid equipment fouling, the untreated bio-oil
 501 can be fed directly without any upgrading process.³² Such integration of biomass-derived
 502 products into the refinery further enhances the circularity of the proposed value chain of the oil
 503 and gas industry. Key assumptions made on the respective biomass integration technology
 504 (product yield, CAPEX, OPEX, energy consumption, and carbon emission) are documented in
 505 Supporting Information **Table S4** and **Table S5**.

506

507 **Figure 7:** Superstructure of biomass retrofitting pathway

508 5 Results & Discussion

509 5.1 Model I: PCA-aided decision-making analysis on biomass integration 510 pathways

511 5.1.1 Dimension reduction

512 The given case study generated 86 possible solutions as described in the superstructure in
513 **Figure 7**. The decision matrix (Z) is established with the corresponding criteria calculated
514 based on the biomass conversion data documented in the Supporting Information (see **Table**
515 **S5**). As such, the formulated matrix is computed into the corresponding PCs to reduce data
516 redundancy. **Figure 8(a)** illustrates that 3 PCs are sufficient to describe the problem (i.e., to
517 achieve $CVAR \geq 90\%$). As such, the respective solution performance scores are evaluated
518 with the 3 PCs (see **Figure 8(b)**). The scatter points represent all the possible solutions and the
519 vectors illustrate the variable loadings to the corresponding PCs.

520

521 **Figure 8:** (a) Pareto Analysis (Dimension Reduction); (b) PCA plot of respective PCs score
522 (scatter) and variable optimize direction (vector)

523 5.1.2 Optimal biomass retrofitting pathway

524 **Figure 9** shows the performance score (based on Equation (19)) of the 5 distinct biomass
525 retrofitting pathways with their respective PCs score. The respective PCs optimization
526 direction is documented in Supporting Information (see **Table S6**). The model favors hydrogen
527 production using gasification (overall degree of satisfaction of 87.54 %) over pyrolysis for bio-
528 oil production (overall degree of satisfaction of 85.58 %). Despite the gasification performing
529 lower in PC2 and PC3 ($u_2 = 11.55\%$, $u_3 = 9.03\%$) relative to pyrolysis pathway ($u_2 = 14.39\%$, $u_3 = 9.67\%$), it offers better revenue potential
531 (\$76 MM/year) as compared to pyrolysis (\$56 MM/year). This contributes to the dominant
532 PC1 (4 % more than pyrolysis) favoring gasification as the optimal solution due to the higher
533 economic value of hydrogen (\$8.102/kg) over bio-fuel (\$0.433/kg). Notably, hydrothermal
534 liquefaction represents an alternative solution to bio-oil production but, the lower production
535 yield (18.02 wt.%) resulted in its pitfall as pyrolysis offer superior performance (26.59 wt.%).
536 This significantly impacted the revenue potential of liquefaction with lower PC1 satisfaction
537 (20.30 % lower than pyrolysis). Similarly, the low product yield of anaerobic digestion
538 (methane yield of 4.75 wt.%) and bioethanol fermentation (bioethanol yield of 9.70 wt.%)

539 limits the revenue potential contributing towards PC1 ($u_1 = 31.28\%$ and 17.44% respectively).
 540 Even though better environmental goals (PC2) are offered by anaerobic digestion ($u_2 = 15.47\%$) and fermentation pathways ($u_2 = 17.87\%$), it is insignificant with diminishing
 541 economic gains ($\Delta u_1 = 35.67\%$ and 49.51% lower, respectively) as compared to gasification.
 542 Overall, the integration of gasification to produce green hydrogen facilities a closed loop
 543 resource achieving CE in O&G industry. The carbon emissions contributed from hydrogen
 544 consumption, operational, and transportation activities are diverted to the plants in the
 545 agriculture industry which further produces biomass as feedstock.
 546

547

548 **Figure 9:** PCs degree of satisfaction of the 5 distinct biomass conversion pathways.

549 Subsequently, there are potential suboptimal solutions which is worth debottlenecking to
 550 identify the root cause that hinders the technology from being selected. As such, parametric
 551 analysis is performed to gain more insights into various decision criteria sensitivity to the
 552 potential suboptimal pathway. This provides researchers and decision makers with insights to
 553 focus resources and efforts on improving the technology with significant impact. Further details
 554 of the respective technology parameters and solutions performance scores are documented in
 555 the Supporting Information (see **Table S7** and **Table S8**).

556 5.1.3 Parametric Analysis

557 Pyrolysis and fermentation pathway are selected as the target of this analysis with modifying
 558 parameters (e.g., product price, yield, carbon emission, CAPEX, OPEX, and energy
 559 consumption). Pyrolysis is one of the sub-optimal solutions that offer a similar degree of
 560 satisfaction (85.58%) as compared to the gasification route (87.54%) (see **Figure 9**). Based
 561 on the sensitivity analysis Based on the sensitivity analysis shown in **Figure 10(a)**, indicates
 562 changes ($\pm 100\%$) in OPEX and production yield (bio-oil) contributes significantly to the PCs
 563 performance score (-10.3% to 10.6% and -20.3% to 46.9% respectively). This signifies
 564 higher sensitivity in production yield and operating cost have a significant influence on the
 565 solution ranking. A slight increase in either production yield or product price (20%) will
 566 debottleneck the model so that the pyrolysis would become the optimal solution (blue region
 567 in **Figure 10(b)**).

568

569 **Figure 10:** Pyrolysis sensitivity analysis (a) Criteria sensitivity to PCs degree of satisfaction
 570 for pyrolysis pathway; (b) Pyrolysis ranking to product yield and OPEX change (blue to red
 571 color gradient indicate ranking from 1 to 10)

572 On the other hand, the model does not favor the biomass fermentation route as the optimal
 573 solution. In fact, it offers the lowest overall PCs degree of satisfaction at 49.2 % among other
 574 pathways (see **Figure 9**). However, biomass fermentation offers an attractive pathway to
 575 integrate bio-ethanol in conventional fuel blends (gasoline and diesel). As such, it is worthwhile
 576 to investigate the potential debottlenecking of this technology so that it can compete with other
 577 biomass integration pathways. Similar to pyrolysis, production yield remains highly influential
 578 (-3.6 % to 17.8 %) to the performance followed by OPEX (-25.4 % to 25.4 %) (see **Figure**
 579 **11(a)**). However, the debottlenecking requirement for the fermentation pathway to becoming
 580 the optimal solution is impractical as a minimum 100 % reduction of OPEX and 100 %
 581 increment in product yield is required (blue region in **Figure 11(b)**). Overall, this indicates the
 582 selection priority of biomass fermentation remains lower compared to other biomass
 583 integration pathway unless significant improvement is achieved in terms of yield and OPEX.

584

585 **Figure 11:** Fermentation sensitivity analysis (a) Criteria sensitivity to PCs degree of
 586 satisfaction for fermentation pathway; (b) Fermentation ranking to product yield and OPEX
 587 change (blue to red color gradient indicate ranking from 1 to 77)

588 **5.2 Model II: Integrated biorefinery facilities location in supply chain**
589 **network**

590 **5.2.1 Case analysis**

591 The facilities location model considers the possible integration of biomass conversion facilities
592 at the supplier (444 palm oil mills), new facility (1,852 designated industrial zones), or demand
593 points (5 crude oil refineries). This resulted in a large problem size (2,301 possible locations)
594 which requires more computational resources and time to solve for the optimal solution. Instead,
595 the problem is separated into 3 sets of facility location problems with each constrained to only
596 consider either (i) palm oil mills (palm oil mill case), (ii) designated industrial zones (new
597 facility case) or, (iii) crude oil refineries (refinery case) as the candidate locations. **Figure 12**
598 indicates the allocation of facilities at suppliers (palm oil mill case) offers the lowest annual
599 cost at \$23.35 MM/year as compared to the case of retrofitting into a crude oil refinery (\$24.75
600 MM/year). This is attributed to the reduction in transportation cost (5.648 % lower) as
601 transporting a large quantity of biomass (1,012,665 tons of EFB) will cost more as compared
602 with the finished product (71,885 tons of liquified hydrogen), despite the higher transport rate
603 (liquified hydrogen \$74 per kg-km to EFB \$17 per kg-km).

604

605 **Figure 12:** Total annual cost of various facility location cases

606 **5.2.2 Optimal facility location**

607 Further evaluation of the palm oil mill case, the optimal number of facilities with respect to the
608 capital and transportation performance are illustrated in **Figure 13**. The increasing number of
609 facilities leads to higher capital investment in new facility but lower transportation cost since
610 shorter travel distance is required. As such, the optimal facility allocation number at 2 is
611 justified by a balanced tradeoff between capital and transportation costs and the overall cost is
612 minimized (indicated with a red dotted line in **Figure 13**). The allocated 2 facilities are
613 illustrated in **Figure 14** (indicated with a 'red star' symbol) with key coordinates and
614 transportation routes. The illustration shows the 2 production facilities allocated in each East
615 and West Malaysia where all the produced products are shipped to satisfy the hydrogen demand
616 of crude oil refineries in the West. This is favorable due to the cost-effectiveness of sea freight
617 as compared to by truck. As shown in **Figure 15**, the increasing number of facilities in West
618 Malaysia (2 facilities in the West to avoid sea freight transport) resulted in higher annual
619 transportation costs (\$2.9 MM/year) due to the longer distance required (200.98 % more than
620 the original allocation).

621

622 **Figure 13:** Annualized cost (capital investment, transportation, and total cost) response to the
 623 number of facilities

624

625 **Figure 14:** Optimal facility location (2 allocated facilities indicated as 'red star' symbol)

626

627 **Figure 15:** Transportation cost of various locations of 2 facilities; (a) Original allocation (1
 628 facility at East and 1 facility at West; (b) Allocate all 2 facilities at East; (c) Allocate all 2
 629 facilities at West

630 **5.2.3 Economic and environmental performance benchmark**

631 The proposed biomass strategy aims to enhance the circularity of the O&G industry where the
 632 economic and environmental performance are benchmarked to justify the effectiveness of the
 633 design model (see **Table 2**). **Figure 16** illustrate the cost breakdown between natural gas-
 634 derived hydrogen (grey \$1.40/kg)⁷³ and biomass-derived hydrogen (green \$1.09/kg) indicating
 635 improved economic performance (32.77 %) of biomass integration strategy. The production
 636 cost of green hydrogen (\$1.09/kg) proposed in this work has major contribution from the
 637 required biomass feedstock (\$0.76/kg H₂; 70.12 %) and operating activities (\$0.23/kg H₂;
 638 20.92 %). This is attributed to the small weight conversion yield of feed (7.1 wt.%) to product,
 639 resulting in large quantity of EFB required (1,012,665 t/year) to satisfy the hydrogen demand
 640 (71,885 t/year) modelled in this work. Notably, the conventional grey hydrogen (\$0.7/kg to
 641 \$2.1/kg) reported to be more affordable than green hydrogen (\$2.6/kg to \$23/kg) in the
 642 literature depending on the type of technology and biomass used⁷³. This is contrary to the
 643 findings in this work, which indicate that green hydrogen can be 22.34 % (\$0.31/kg) cheaper
 644 than conventional grey hydrogen. The proposition of integrated biorefinery offer economic
 645 benefit in operational (71.46 % lower) and capital (54.29 % lower). As such, the modelled work
 646 indicates comparable hydrogen price considering possible higher carbon penalty for grey
 647 hydrogen.

648 **Table 2:** Economic and environmental performance

Hydrogen Source	Linear Economy (Grey Hydrogen)	Circular Economy (Green Hydrogen)
Production Cost of Hydrogen	\$1.40/kg H ₂	\$1.09/kg H ₂
Carbon Emission of Hydrogen	10.00 kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂	1.32 kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂

649

650 **Figure 16:** Cost breakdown comparison between grey and green hydrogen.⁷⁴

651 The environmental performance of the proposed strategy is estimated at 1.32 kg CO₂ per kg of
 652 hydrogen with 87.32 % (82,667,809 kg CO₂/year) attributed to the production and 12.68 %
 653 (12,004,779 kg CO₂/year) from transportation activities. As expected, biomass-derived
 654 hydrogen produces lower emissions as compared to natural gas-derived hydrogen which is
 655 accounted for 9 to 11 kg CO₂/kg.⁷³ In fact, since biomass was used as the feedstock, part of the
 656 emissions is biogenic which will not add additional burden to the environment unlike those
 657 emitted from fossil fuels-based feedstock. Overall, the transition towards green hydrogen
 658 production suggests superior environmental performance indicating an 86.8 % reduction in
 659 carbon emissions.

660 **6 Conclusion**

661 Overall, this work proposes a biomass integration strategy to address the ideal technology
 662 pathway and facility location to empower circularity in the O&G industry. Hydrogen
 663 production using gasification is recommended by the model as the ideal integration pathway
 664 attributed by the promising revenue potential of hydrogen production. The adapted case study
 665 demonstrates the proposed biomass integration strategy with environmental (1.34 kg CO₂/kg
 666 H₂; 86 % reduction) and economic advantage (\$1.09/kg H₂; 22.34 % cheaper). The economic
 667 major contributor from feedstock (70.12 %) and OPEX (20.92 %) suggest key development in
 668 biomass discount value to achieve better economic goals. The O&G CE is achieved through
 669 the circulation of carbon emission associated to green hydrogen consumption diverted to
 670 biomass generation which in turn are converted back to hydrogen. As such, the presented
 671 results are served as a recommendation for stakeholders, policymakers and, fellow researchers
 672 to expand the addressed problems to their respective case studies encouraging the
 673 implementation of CE. It is noteworthy the formulated model is easily expandable to new
 674 technology and facility locations given the data availability which is adaptable to various case
 675 studies.

676 However, the developed model represents the exploratory stage of the strategy development
 677 process. Challenge remains for extensive research to address the various uncertainties (e.g.,
 678 carbon capture and heat integration potential, supply and demand stability, storage and
 679 transport options) to better convince decision makers to commit towards the strategy
 680 implementation. From the research perspective, the extension towards a market evaluation

681 through predictive analysis will provide a better understanding of the supply and demand
682 behavior which aids to yield more reliable and accurate findings for decision-makers. Moreover,
683 the extension towards multi-period optimization can consider the fluctuating biomass supplies
684 to better simulate a realistic biomass supply chain behavior in the model accounting for storage
685 and production schedule. Furthermore, the evaluation of various transportation modes (pipe,
686 truck, gaseous, liquified product) considering the various technical limitation (e.g., pump
687 limitation, transport efficiency, cost per distance, etc.) and geographical terrain difficulty (e.g.,
688 mountain, swamp, forest density, etc.) enable more comprehensive optimization that can
689 generate a more realistic supply-chain design towards various cases while maintaining
690 environmental interest (deforestation, tunnelling, etc.). Notably, this work demonstrates the
691 effectiveness of the novel PCA-aided optimization approach to address the MODM problem
692 in biomass technology selection. Another potential extension is to benchmark the method with
693 other existing MODM approaches (e.g., Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to
694 Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), VlseKriterijumska Optimizacija
695 I Kompromisno Resenje (VIKOR), etc.) to gain more insights about the obtained solutions.
696 Besides, improvement can also be made to the PCA-aided optimization in observing the
697 possibility of the rank reversal phenomenon to ensure the reliability and scalability of the
698 methodology.

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706 **Supporting Information**

707 The Supporting Information is available free of charge at

- 708 • Biomass conversion technology data and modelling parameters. Detailed model results
709 and reference to model source code (Doc).

710 **Reference**

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953 **Synopsis**

954 This study explores biomass integration technology in the oil and gas industry to promote
955 circularity, employing analytical methods to optimize technology and supply chain problem.